

Constructing Industrial Clusters and Regulations in Industrial Cluster (IC) Development

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ABSTRACT

In Hanoi, there are currently 70 industrial clusters (CCNs) operating, contributing significantly to economic growth and ensuring social security. Hanoi has good infrastructure in terms of traffic, electricity, water, post office, etc. Besides, Hanoi has been invested heavily in infrastructure development, this is a good condition. to develop CCNs (industrial clusters). CCN is the geographical concentration of production - business establishments, organizations related to each other in terms of production, use of infrastructure and limiting environmental pollution. Therefore, CCN can be considered as the focal point for implementing internal linkages between industries and services and linking industry with rural areas in the region and locality. Therefore, CCN is the nucleus that promotes regional and local socio-economic development.

Keywords: IC development; Industrial clusters; Regulations; Shortcomings.

1. Introduction

First of all, according to DECREE No: 68/2017/ND-CP

Hanoi, May 25, 2017 - ON MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL Clusters - In this Decree, the following terms are construed as follows:

1. An industrial cluster is a place of production and provision of services for industrial production and handicrafts, with definite geographical boundaries, no inhabitant, invested and built in order to attract, relocate small and medium enterprises, cooperatives and cooperative groups to invest in production and business.

The industrial cluster has an area not exceeding 75 ha and not less than 10 ha. Particularly for industrial clusters in mountainous districts and industrial clusters in craft villages with an area not exceeding 75 ha and not less than 5 ha.

2. Craft village industrial cluster means an industrial cluster serving the relocation and expansion of production and business activities of small and medium-sized enterprises, cooperatives, cooperative groups, household and individual production establishments in the village, occupations in order to overcome environmental pollution, develop professions and craft villages in the locality.

3. Investors in construction of technical infrastructure of industrial clusters are enterprises, cooperatives and units established and operating in accordance with Vietnamese law, investing in construction, management and exploitation system of technical infrastructure works for industrial clusters.

4. District-level industrial cluster development center is a non-business economic unit with revenue directly under the district-level People's Committee, which has been established under the Regulation on management of industrial clusters promulgated together with Decision No. 105/ 2009/QD-TTg dated August 19, 2009 of the Prime Minister.

5. The district-level industrial cluster management board is a unit directly under the district-level People's Committee, established by decision of the district-level People's Committee to assign or authorize the investor to build the cluster's technical infrastructure of the industry in the area.

6. The system of general technical infrastructure works of the industrial cluster includes the system of internal traffic works, sidewalks, trees, water supply, drainage, wastewater treatment, solid waste, and electricity supply, public lighting, internal communication, operator, security and other works serving the operation of the industrial cluster.

7. Organizations and individuals investing in production and business in industrial clusters, including enterprises, cooperatives and cooperative groups established in accordance with Vietnamese law; individuals and households (for industrial clusters and craft villages) have business registration in accordance with the law.

2. Methodology

Authors have used qualitative and analytical methods, descriptive method for primary model, synthesis and discussion methods in this paper.

We also used historical materialism method.

3. Main findings

3.1. Background

CCN is the geographical concentration of production - business establishments, organizations related to each other in terms of production, use of infrastructure and limiting environmental pollution. Therefore, CCN can be considered as the focal point for implementing internal linkages between industries and services and linking industry with rural areas in the region and locality. Therefore, CCN is the nucleus that promotes regional and local socio-economic development.

Figure 1. Hanoi develop ICs

(SOURCE: Internet)

3.2. Relevant Regulations

Article 7. Conditions for adjustment and supplementation of the industrial cluster development planning.

Conditions for adjusting industrial clusters out of the planning: An industrial cluster that meets one of the following two conditions shall be considered and removed from the Planning:

a) The industrial cluster is no longer consistent with the socio-economic development planning; Industrial and handicraft development planning; Land use planning and plans; Construction and urban planning and other industry and product planning in the area;

b) There is a need to convert an industrial cluster with effective investment in low-tech infrastructure for the purpose of developing other fields and industries according to the orientation of socio-economic development planning, construction and urban planning. in the area approved by the competent authority.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

According to Document (CIRCULARS) No: 28/2020/TT-BCT

Hanoi, November 16, 2020

PROVISIONS AND INSTRUCTIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF SOME CONTENT OF DECREE NO. 68/2017/ND-CP DATE MAY 25, 2017 OF THE GOVERNMENT ON MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL Clusters AND DECREE No. 66/2020/ND-- CP JUNE 11, 2020 OF THE GOVERNMENT AMENDING AND SUPPLEMENTING SOME ARTICLES OF DECREE NO. 68/2017/ND-CP

Section 2. INVESTMENT IN TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE OF INDUSTRIAL Clusters

Article 4. Selection of enterprises and cooperatives as investors in construction of technical infrastructure of industrial clusters

1. To receive and select enterprises and cooperatives as investors in the construction of technical infrastructure of industrial clusters in the locality:

a) Immediately after receiving the written request to act as the investor in the construction of technical infrastructure of industrial clusters from the enterprise or cooperative, the district-level People's Committee shall notify the receipt and the time for making the successful application. establish and expand industrial clusters on local mass media;

b) The decision on establishment and expansion of an industrial cluster (including the assignment of enterprises or cooperatives as investors in the construction of technical infrastructure of the industrial cluster) is announced on the mass media of the enterprise. immediately after being signed by the provincial People's Committee for promulgation.

2. The selection of enterprises and cooperatives as investors in the construction of technical infrastructure of industrial clusters is a content of appraisal of the establishment and expansion of industrial clusters. The time for

selecting an investor to build technical infrastructure is within the period of appraising the application for the establishment and expansion of the industrial cluster.

3. The Investor Selection Evaluation Council (hereinafter referred to as the Council):

a) During the appraisal of dossiers of establishment and expansion of industrial clusters, the Department of Industry and Trade shall report to the provincial-level People's Committees to decide on the establishment of a Council, including: The Chairman of the Council is the leader of the provincial-level People's Committee. , the Vice Chairman of the Council is the leader of the Department of Industry and Trade, the Secretary of the Council is the representative of the professional management department of the Department of Industry and Trade, the members of the Council are the representatives of the Departments of Planning and Investment, the Department of Natural Resources and Environment. school, Department of Construction, Department of Finance and some other relevant agencies and units (if necessary);

b) The Council conducts evaluation and selection of investors to build technical infrastructure of industrial clusters when there are at least 2/3 members participating, following the scoring method with a 100-point scale for the methodological criteria. investment projects for construction of technical infrastructure (maximum 15 points), plans for management and environmental protection of industrial clusters (maximum 15 points), capacity and experience of enterprises and cooperatives (maximum of 15 points) 30 points) and financial plan for investment and construction of technical infrastructure (maximum 40 points). Based on the actual conditions of the locality, the Department of Industry and Trade shall report to the Council to agree on the principles and working methods of the Council, the contents of each criterion and the corresponding score level of those contents. be suitable;

c) The evaluation score for selection of investor in the construction of technical infrastructure of an industrial cluster shall be decided by the Council, presented in writing and signed by the Council's Chairman (or the Council's Vice Chairman if approved by the Council's Chairman). Board of Trustees), secretary of the Council and members of the Board to participate;

Figure 2. ICs development

(SOURCE: Internet)

Enterprises and cooperatives with score books of 50 or more may be considered and assigned as investors in the construction of technical infrastructure of industrial clusters. In case there are two or more enterprises or cooperatives that jointly request to be the investor in the construction of technical infrastructure, the enterprise or cooperative with the highest score shall be selected; if there are two or more enterprises or cooperatives with the same score, the Council shall unanimously propose to select one enterprise or cooperative as the investor in the construction of technical infrastructure of the industrial cluster.

d) The Council is responsible to the People's Committee of the province for the results of evaluation and selection of investors in the construction of technical infrastructure of the industrial cluster.

Declarations

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors have declared no competing interests.

Consent for Publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this study.

Authors' Contributions

All the authors took part in literature review, research and manuscript writing equally.

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